

DISTRIBUTION OF HELMINTHIC DISEASES OF LIVESTOCK IN THE NORTHERN REGIONS OF THE REPUBLIC OF KARAKALPAKSTAN

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Abstract:

This article describes the helminthic diseases and some parasitic diseases found in rabbits in livestock farms and in cattle and sheep of various breeds in Takhtakopir, Takhiatosh and Shumanay districts of the Republic of Karakalpakstan, which is the northern region of our Republic.

Annotatsiya:

Ushbu maqolada Respublikamizning shimoliy hududi bo'lgan Qoraqalpog'iston Respublikasining Taxtako'pir, Taxiatosh va Shumanay tumanlaridagi chorvachilik xo'jaliklarda hamda aholi qo'lida boqilayotgan turli zotli qoramol va qo'ylarda uchraydigan gelmintoz kasalliklari hamda quyonlarda uchraydigan ayrim parizitar kasalliklar bayon etilgan.

Key words: Cattle, sheep, rabbit, helminth, helminthosis, trematodosis, cestodosis, nematodosis, fasciolosis, monesiosis, strongyliatosis, marshallagiosis, nematodirosis, invasion, coccidiosis.

Relevance of the topic. It is known that today's rapidly developing and changing world economy and the increase in the population in the whole world, including in our country, lead to an increase in the demand for livestock products.

Animal husbandry is an important branch of our country's agriculture, providing employment and income to our rural population.

At the same time, the livestock industry is important in meeting the domestic consumer market's need for ecologically clean and high-quality livestock products - meat and milk, as well as products made from them.

Based on the above, today in our Republic, great attention is being paid to the further development of the livestock sector, most importantly, to increase the number of cattle, increase productivity, increase the weight of breeding cattle in the herd due to the introduction of scientific achievements to all livestock sectors, and to increase the production of ecologically clean and high-quality livestock products.

The State program for the implementation of the strategy for the development of our country in 2022-2026 defines very important tasks for the development of animal husbandry on a scientific basis and the further improvement of veterinary services for livestock, as well as ensuring the stability of the epizootic situation.

Protection of livestock, especially cattle and sheep, from various infectious, non-infectious and invasive diseases, especially helminthiasis, remains one of the most important tasks in the implementation of the tasks set in the field.

The purpose of the research. To study the prevalence of helminthic diseases among cattle and sheep in some districts of the Republic of Karakalpakstan.

Research object and methods . The researches were carried out on livestock farms of Takhtakopir, Takhyatosh and Shumanay districts of the Republic of Karakalpakstan and cattle of various breeds, sheep and partly rabbits. Inspection was carried out by examination of dung samples taken from animals by helmintoovoscopic (Flyborn, rewash) methods.

Research results and their analysis: According to the results of the conducted research, the dynamics of infestation with helminths in some districts of the Republic of Karakalpakstan is reflected in the following tables:

Level of helminth infection of sheep of different breeds and Holstein cattle kept under the care of the population and in livestock farms in Takhtakopir district of the Republic of Karakalpakstan

Table 1

Animal Type and breed	Number of animals examined (head)	Number of infected animals (head)	Invasion Extent (Percentage)
Merinos sheep (quoted from the Kyrgyz Republic in September 2021)	22	21	95.4
Local population sheep	36	1	2.8
Mother sheep of the Karakyl breed (bought in 2020 from Navoi, Kashkadarya and Surkhandarya regions)	50	30	60.0
Karakol lambs	50	6	12.0
Holstein cattle (bought from Germany in May 2021)	9	2	22.2
Total:	167	60	Average: 35.9

Table 1 shows that the prevalence of helminthiasis among sheep of different breeds is different and significantly different from each other.

Performed a helmintooscopic examination of **Merinos sheep** purchased from Kyrgyzstan in September 2021 by "Beltov qorako'lichilik klasteri" in Takhtakopir District of the Republic of Karakalpakstan, 8 out of 22 heads of sheep had marshallagiosis (36.4%). Nematodiriosis at the beginning of 7 (31.8%), 5 heads were infected with other gastro-intestinal strongylotoses (22.7%), and 1 head of sheep was infected with moneziosis (4.5%), the total extent of invasion was 95.4%.

Among sheep of the local breed population, 1 out of 36 examined sheep had another type of gastrointestinal strongylatosis, and the total extent of infection was 2.8%. ewes purchased from the cattle breeding farms of Navoi, Kashkadarya and Surkhandarya regions by the Karakol breeding experimental station in the district had marshallagiosis (4.0%), 7 **nematodiriosis** (14.0%), and other gastrointestinal diseases in 5 heads. strongylatosis (10.0%) and fasciolosis (32.0%) were found in 16 sheep, the total extent of infestation was 60.0%, and helmintooscopic examination of dung samples from 50 Karakol lambs revealed nematodiriosis in 5 sheep (10.0%), fasciolosis (2.0%) was detected in 1 lamb, and the extent of invasion was 12.0%.

During the examination of 9 empty Holstein cattle purchased from Germany in 21021 by "Siyt Chorva" cattle farm in the district, nematodiriosis (11.1%) and other gastro-intestinal strongylatosis (11.1%) were found in 1 empty cattle and infestation extensiveness was 22.2 percent. out of 167 free cattle that were checked in Takhtakopir district, and the extent of infestation was 35.9% on average.

Infestation of various breeds of cattle and sheep with helminths and rabbits with parasites under the care of the population and livestock farms in Takhi Atosh district of the Republic of Karakalpakstan

Table 2

Animal Type and breed	Number of animals examined (head)	Number of infected animals (head)	Invasion Extent (Percentage)
Rabbits white giant breed (bought from Russia in 2016)	24	11	45.8
Cattle of the local population	13	3	23.1
Suffolk sheep (bought from Ireland in June 2021)	30	4	13.3
Total:	67	18	Average: 26.9

Table 2 shows the results of inspection of rabbits, cattle and sheep in Takhiatosh district of the Republic of Karakalpakstan.

In 2016, when we conducted a helmintooscopic examination of 24 white giant rabbits bought from Russia by the private entrepreneur "Intizor-Dilnora" in the district, 10 of them had coccidiosis (eimeria) (41.7%), 1 of them had nematodiriosis (4.1%), the extent of invasion was 45, 8 percent, when 13 head of domestic cattle were examined, 2 head of cattle were infected with fasciolosis (15.4%), 1 head was infected with moneziosis (7.7%), the extent of infestation was 23.1%.

During the examination of 30 sheep of the Suffolk breed purchased from Ireland in June 2021 by the "Beltoy" APJ farm in the district, it was found that 3 sheep were infected with other gastrointestinal strongylatosis (10.0%), 1 sheep was infected with fasciolosis (3.3%) , the extent of invasion was 13.3 percent. Out of a total of 67 livestock examined from this district, 18 were infected with parasites to varying degrees, and the extent of infestation was 26.9% on average.

Infestation of cattle of various breeds under the care of the population and in livestock farms in Shumanay district of the Republic of Karakalpakstan with helminthosis

Table 3

Animal Type	Number of animals examined (head)	Number of infected animals (head)	Invasion Extent (Percentage)
Local breed of cattle	18	1	5.6
Holstein cattle (bought from Austria in September 2021)	22	8	36.4
Total:	40	9	Average: 22.5

Table 3 shows the results of helmintooscopic examination of dung samples taken from livestock farms and cattle under the care of the population in Shumanay district of the Republic of Karakalpakstan.

According to the results of inspections, 1 head of 18 head of domestic cattle under the care of the population had other gastrointestinal strongylatosis (5.6%), samples taken from 22 heads of "Holstein" cattle purchased from Austria in September 2021 by the "Ganesha Milk" livestock farm of the district during the inspection, it was noted that 8 head of cattle were infected with fasciolosis (36.4%) to varying degrees.

9 out of 40 examined cattle were infected with helminthiasis, and the average extent of infestation was 22.5%.

Infestation of sheep, cattle and rabbits of various breeds under the care of the population and livestock farms in some districts of the Republic of Karakalpakstan with helminthosis general indicators on

Table 4

Animal Tour	Number of animals checked (head)	Number of infected animals	Invasion extensiveness (percentage)
Different breeds of sheep	188	52	27.6
Cattle of various breeds	62	14	22.6
Rabbits	24	11	45.8
Total:	274	77	Average: 28.1

Table 4 summarizes and analyzes the studies in the 3 districts where the above inspections were conducted. A total of 188 sheep of different breeds were examined

helminthooscopically, and 52 sheep were found to be infected in various degrees, and the extent of infestation was 27.6% .

When 62 cattle of different breeds were examined, 14 cattle were infected with helminths, the extent of infestation was 22.6%, and when 24 rabbits were examined, 11 rabbits were infected, 1 of them were infected with helminths, and 10 were infected with coccidiosis (eimeria). infected, and the extent of invasion was 45.8%.

Out of a total of 274 heads of livestock, 77 heads of different levels of infestation were detected, and it was found that the total extent of infestation was 28.1% on average.

Brief conclusions

1. According to the results of helminthoscopic examination in the districts of the Republic of Karakalpakstan where the inspections were carried out, the extent of infestation in sheep of different ages was observed to increase depending on the age of the animal.

2. Invasion extent It was found that different breeds of cattle purchased from abroad are slightly more infected with helminths compared to local breeds.

It is known that this situation is directly related to the age of livestock, the season of the year, climatic conditions and the degree to which the treatment and preventive measures were carried out. .

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